

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The government of Uzbekistan has identified 10 languages, among which it is necessary to choose two compulsory to study in schools: English, Russian, German, French, Chinese, Korean, Japanese, Turkish, Arabic and Farsi. As studies have shown, most Uzbeks study Russian, but over the last year the number of those who want to learn English has increased significantly. In this article is considered a brief history of the development of English language in the Republic of Uzbekistan from 1997-2021.*

Keywords: *"Education Law", EF English Proficiency Index, a highly skilled workforce, migrants, resolution, integration, GDP, competitive ability, patent, association, Scientific and Technical Transformation.*

РОЛЬ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Аннотация. *Правительство Узбекистана определило 10 языков, среди которых необходимо выбрать два обязательных для изучения в школах: английский, русский, немецкий, французский, китайский, корейский, японский, турецкий, арабский и фарси. Как показали исследования, большинство узбекистанцев изучают русский язык, но за последний год количество желающих выучить английский значительно увеличилось. В данной статье рассматривается краткая история развития английского языка в Республике Узбекистан с 1997-2021 гг.*

Ключевые слова: *«Образовательное право», EF English Proficiency Index, высококвалифицированная рабочая сила, мигранты, разрешение, интеграция, ВВП, конкурентоспособность, патент, ассоциация, научно-техническая трансформация.*

Uzbekistan is actively integrating into the global education system. The tumultuous changes sweeping over the CIS countries, reflected in all areas of life of the countries, have also affected the higher education system of Uzbekistan, which has entered the world arena. One of the strategic goals of the country is to join the ranks of developed, democratic States, to provide its people with favorable conditions for life and prosperity and to take a worthy place in the world community. In recent decades, the Republic of Uzbekistan has paid great attention to the education system. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to train competitive, creative specialists, fluent in foreign languages. Increasing global competition in the world determines the availability of highly qualified personnel as the central factor of progress. The formation of human resources potential of the country becomes a priority, so one of the first steps of the independent country was the development and adoption of the National Program for Personnel Training. "Education Act" adopted in 1997, and the "National Personnel Training Program" in 1997. New relationships are also actively developing from day to day. Both in society and in education there is an intensive development of communication practices, the development of the spread of advanced technologies. All this is blurring national boundaries not only economically, but also linguistically. English as the language of the computer, international conferences, tourism, where people of all nationalities participate and use English as a means of communication, with scientific purposes, on official need and for recreation, has become the

most widespread. Knowledge of the language and computer literacy increase opportunities for professional development. The younger generation is in the focus of constant attention of the President, who sees young people as the promising future of Uzbekistan. According to UNICEF monitoring report for 2003, the youth under the age of 17 made up 11 out of 26 million people of Uzbekistan 42% of the total population. The documents on the development of education include the Presidential Decree No. PP-1875 of December 10, 2012, foreign language is studied in the system of continuous education since 2013, starting from the first grade of general secondary school to postgraduate education.

In May 2021, Shavkat Mirziyoyev issued a decree on the compulsory study of foreign languages in schools. Against this background, over the past year, the demand for English language learning has noticeably increased. Last May, Uzbek President Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted a law requiring school leavers to master at least two foreign languages. In addition to schoolchildren, learning at least one foreign language is becoming a requirement for those who want to be officials or are already in public service. Proficiency in foreign languages will help Uzbekistan become more competitive in the global market, Mirziyoyev said. Provided a significant portion of the country's GDP is devoted to international translations, such a strategy is reasonable and justified. In this year's EF English Proficiency Index, Uzbekistan ranked 88th out of 122 countries. The current stage is also the expansion of international cooperation, which is seen as one of the mechanisms of achieving the goals of the national program.

The system of teaching foreign languages is aimed at forming a harmoniously developed, highly educated, creatively thinking younger generation, contributing to the further integration of the republic into the global community by training specialists fluent in the Internet and foreign languages. New requirements imposed by global competition, face problems, one of which is the lack of professionally-oriented textbooks of foreign languages, as well as the need for fluency in a foreign language specialist to be in demand and competitive in the labor market. Without knowledge of a foreign language it is impossible to move around the countries. A qualified specialist who does not speak a foreign language cannot be in demand outside of Uzbekistan. English language has acquired the character of a global language, as the language not only of business and international communication, but also of political, cultural, scientific and technical transformations and achievements, the language of patents, documentation, computer technology. Knowledge of English is of practical importance for the growth of a specialist. The important purpose of educational reforms in the modern world is to increase the standard of professional knowledge, increase the competitiveness of a specialist, for which the knowledge of languages is necessary. Such languages as English, Russian, Arabic are international languages in which business, cultural, political meetings, scientific conferences are conducted. English is the language of tourism and entertainment; 80% of Internet sites and 90% of publications are in English, the Internet is a source of information about the latest scientific and technological achievements. Only such a specialist can be in demand on the labor market and be successful in his or her future activities. In this regard, the management of the process of shaping the professional qualities of a specialist is especially important. It is especially necessary now when business, political, cultural contacts are developing so rapidly, international organizations, communities, associations, joint ventures, firms, banks are being created. Demand for a foreign language is especially high for modern professions - businessman, banker, journalist, doctor, athlete, lawyer - all of them for successful activities need to know a foreign language, which will

allow them to be in demand as professionals. The purpose of foreign language instruction is to prepare students to use that language in their future profession. It is important to build a system of teaching at a new quality level by selecting the language material and improving the forms and methods, to achieve through the teaching of a foreign language effective impact on learning, beliefs, behavior, future employment Language is a product of a developing society, an indicator of people's culture, reflecting their mentality.

The result of this study shows that the English language increases the number of highly qualified specialists and the competitiveness of personnel in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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